

GlossAPI: Architecturing the Greek Data Pile for LLM development

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Abstract

With the release of large language models such as ChatGPT, there has been a surge in demand for national language data sources. Greek language resources, in particular, have become widely available and are frequently discussed in the context of LLM development for tailored or custom use. The development of large language models presents several challenges, one of which is data preparation, which must be of high quality and grounded in linguistic, conceptual, and historical foundations. Creating data sets of this nature is a highly complex task. This study focuses on the collection, curation, and management of data sets for the Greek language, as well as making the data provision for use in training custom Greek LLMs smoother, not only for custom LLM development but also for fine-tuning existing LLM models. Immediately after the ChatGPT invention, the GlossAPI project initiative started in 2023. This research encourages the need for a Greek data pile creation, which is further dependent upon the data collection, acquisition, data cleaning, annotation, and classification steps. Upon cleaning the data pile, storage of the data pile and serving it to the LLMs or other users is the main concern. This concern is resolved by the use of an integrative, capable database solution that can facilitate in-database inference, including data collection, annotation, classification, and storage. For each of these stages, a special protocol requires, for instance, the use of existing LLMs or other artificial intelligence models for data preprocessing, annotation, and classification. To store data, we need a database that can seamlessly integrate with other data resources. Our study aim at the development of an architecture to unite Greek data pile and intelligent AI models at a one place using MindsDB integrative capabilities. MindsDB is an emerging database with an integration functionality to wide variety of AI models which can facilitate the data processing, annotation,

classification through the integration of Supervised, unsupervised, and even though LLMs models.

CCS Concepts

• **Applied computing** → Information integration and interoperability; Digital libraries and archives.

Keywords

Large Language Models, Pre-Trained Language Models, Generative Pre-Trained Transformers, Natural Language Processing, Large Scale Language Corpora

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1 Introduction

Large language models emerged with transformative capabilities in the realm of natural language models not only for natural language understanding but also for the natural language generation [15]. Large language models are super flexible and scalable in contrast to the smaller models, which shows the LLMs' potential for the further expansion of these models [19]. LLMs have shown a high-level generalization across different tasks such as language processing in different languages such as French, Greek, and Spanish and also computer vision [21]. The quality and quantity of data required for LLMs training impact its capability, expansion, and generalization. Generally, the larger the dataset the better the outcomes [18]. Several studies highlight the language scarcity for the large language models training. Öhman et. al. (20023) presents a data pile for Nordic languages (Danish, Icelandic, Norwegian, and Swedish) as well as high-quality English data. Keeping in mind all these multi-lingual large language models developed around the globe, there is a clear need for the creation of a Greek Language data pile. At present some ongoing efforts for Greek models already exist

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such as the Meltemi Greek large language development by Athena Research Centre

¹ and GreekBART [3].

However, Greece’s readiness to contribute a fully open-source Greek LLM remains limited mainly due to political and strategic choices that extend several decades into the past. Currently, efforts for Greek LLM do not fully comply with the open source AI definition² despite having high-quality data for their training. Overall, the open-source community remains disempowered in terms of access to high quality open data. Thus, the creation of an open, ethically acquired, mechanically accessible, and representative body of training examples of the Greek language remains and will remain an end in itself for the open software community and beyond. So, our efforts led to exactly this: the de-editing and recording of the available sources in Greek with permission to reuse. But there is a paradox in this: Any data that is easily accessible, is already in a machine-readable form, or is labeled in some way, will surely have already found its way into existing language models. Most data of high linguistic value on the historicity and variety of the Greek language, which also reflect the various textual genres and varieties of its use, are to some extent digitized, but in the majority of cases not mechanically accessible, either due to user-unfriendly construction of the website navigation, either because the visual character recognition is absent, or because there are no re-use permissions.

Creating the Greek language pile requires mixed effort of humans and machines at several stages: data collection, preprocessing, annotation, and classification. In this study, a smart pipeline to reduce the human efforts in the creation of Greek language data pile and integrating the machine efforts or computer aided efforts into the process with help of intelligent databases such as MindsDB³. There are also requirements for better data management in large language models, because it’s a massive data sets which are hard to manage in a better way [18]. The availability of intelligent or in-database inference technologies in the process of Greek data pile development can ease these stages of data collection, preprocessing, annotation, and classification with better integration to other applications, models, and resources through the use of APIs. The high quality and quantity Greek data is not only an important part of the adoption of advanced language technologies in the context of e-government. It is immediately possible, and to some extent possible, that public services utilize these technologies either to serve the citizen through digital assistants or to handle their internal processes that would otherwise require a lot of human effort.

Keeping in view all these efforts, our study has three research objectives:

- **RO1: Creation:** Greek Data pile
- **RO2: Data management:** massive data collection, storage, preprocessing, annotation, and classification with intelligent and in-database inference tool
- **RO3:** An architecture for the creation of Greek open data pile for the LLMs development using the RO1 and RO2 as a basis.

¹<https://www.athenarc.gr/en/new-athena-project-meltemi>

²<https://opensource.org/deepdive/drafts/the-open-source-ai-definition-1-0-rc1>

³<https://mindsdb.com>

The remaining manuscript has been organized into sections. Section 2 contains the research background and describes various related concepts. In Section 3, the proposed methodology has been shown and explained in distinct steps. Section 4 is reserved for the presentation of results and analysis performed by adopting the proposed methodology. Section 5 is dedicated to the discussion of the findings of this study. Finally, Section 6 quotes the conclusion of this research and future directions of the research.

2 Research background

LLMs applications: Natural language processing has been transformed by Large Language Models (LLMs), which have exhibited exceptional capabilities in a variety of tasks [14, 22]. Different evaluation benchmarks have proven the close to human-level performance of LLMs because of their transformer architectures [1]. Up to their usage, LLMs are applicable in a variety of practical and research fields, not limited to education, healthcare, government, and businesses [8, 14]. LLMs revolutionize not only in the processing of textual data but also for the images, which makes them large vision models. For instance, in radiology, LLMs can process text and images at once [1]. In governments, LLMs have the potential to provide services to the end-users in an effective and efficient way. Loukis et. al. 2023, discusses the ChatGPT applications in relation to Open Governments and services [8]. Large Language Models (LLMs) like ChatGPT have demonstrated impressive performance in various tasks, including text translation, product categorization, sentiment analysis, and information extraction [9]. LangChain is helping in the creation of LLM applications to provide the end-users a flawless conversation interface. LangChain is openly available and supports the freehand development and customisation pipeline with modular solutions [17]. All these positive impacts and applications of LLMs with outstanding impacts, they also face challenges that require solid mitigation plans, such as data and hardware resources [1].

Data piles and LLMs: Recent research has focused on datasets used for training large language models (LLMs). A thorough survey categorized these datasets into five types: pre-training corpora, fine-tuning instruction, preference, evaluation, and traditional NLP datasets [7]. LLMs needed a vast amount of data to generate the knowledge or more text in fluent and effective manner [25]. Creating language specific large language models requires efforts in creation of datasets by translation of large corpus of other language e.g. for instance English to Greek [25]. The lack of multilingual datasets was tackled through the creation of CulturaX, which contains 6.3 trillion tokens across 167 languages [10]. The LMSYS-Chat-1M dataset, comprising one million real-world conversations with 25 large language models, was used to further investigate user interactions and to develop models for content moderation, safety benchmarking, and instruction-following [24]. ToolQA is a dataset designed to improve large language models’ question-answering abilities and their interaction with external tools [26]. Similarly, examples of data piles created for training large language models include “The Nordic Pile: A 1.2TB Nordic Dataset for Language Modeling” [12], “The Pile: An 800GB Dataset of Diverse Text for Language Modeling,” [4] and “MultiLegalPile: A 689GB Multilingual Legal Corpus [11].” Our work can expand the Greek language

data pile by adding more context to the data available for LLMs training and fine-tuning.

Data preparations for LLMs: Several studies present the data preparations tools for the LLMs such as Data-Juicer is a system designed to facilitate the efficient creation and evaluation of diverse data recipes for training large language models [2]. Data annotation is an important part of the LLMs training and also part of data preparations, in which data is labelled with required information which is useful to increase the efficiency of models in return, a survey explores the usage of LLMs for the data annotation automatically, also LLM-Generated Annotations Assessment, and LLM-Generated Annotations Utilization [16]. Synthetic data generation with the help of generative AI models and their usage for LLM training has been seen in the industry. One of the very examples is DataDreamer, a tool that is being used for synthetic data production [13]. Studies elaborate on the requirement of selection of datasets for pretraining purposes of the LLMs. Xie et al. (2023) categorise pretraining data selection for general-domain models such as ChatGPT and domain-specific ones like Codex. ChatGPT is general purpose and Codex⁴ is used to translate natural language into code. They highlight the challenge in finding the best-fit target data sample from a huge, raw, complex, and even unlabeled data corpus. Language and curation experts help in the identification of target datasets; it also depends on the data complexity. In their study, they proposed a resampling technique to enhance the data selection efficiency for language models [20].

Studies have highlighted the usage of LLMs for data preparation and cleaning modules. It has been noticed their usage specifically for data noise detection, data imputation, and matching schemas and entities [23]. Researchers have introduced methods for preparing datasets that include creating paragraph chunks, question-answer pairs, and keyword-paragraph chunk pairs for documentation, as well as summary-function pairs for code [5]. Nasser et al., 2023 explore the effectiveness of OpenAI’s ChatGPT for data preparation tasks, demonstrating its strong performance in text translation, product categorization, sentiment classification, and information extraction, while noting challenges with noisy data and complex reasoning [9]. Despite their capabilities, LLMs often encounter difficulties with intricate reasoning and specialized knowledge, and they may yield inaccurate outputs when presented with noisy or ambiguous information [9].

Greek LLMs and training: With the surge of multilingual LLM development in the world, there have been a number of initiatives around the development of Greek LLMs for both public and private sectors. One recent example of this surge is Meltemi—the first Greek LLM model, built on top of the Mistral 7B architecture, is now on the market. For the development of Meltemi, they utilized existing resources such as, Wikipedia, ELRC-SHARE, EUR-LEX & MultiEUR-LEX, MaCoCu, parliamentary proceedings, HPLT, full texts (e.g., theses and dissertations), and abstracts from Greek academic repositories. Additionally, they incorporated pre-filtered resources originally compiled from the web, including the CulturaX corpus [25]. To prepare the Greek data for Meltemi, they performed a number of steps such as data collection, acquisition,

noise reduction, and duplicate removal. After this invention, several organisations thought to transform their environment and integrate LLM solutions into their specific use cases. However, this transformation is not smooth because of the unavailability of suitable Greek datasets for LLM training. To fill up this research and practical gap in the development of Greek LLM, this study aims to contribute to the development of Greek data pile with joint effort with Open Technology Alliance (GFOSS). After ChatGPT was introduced, GFOSS well understood the requirement of the Greek Data pile and initiated the GlossAPI project. Combined efforts are required from humans and machines to prepare the Greek data pile. For instance, data collection, acquisition, preprocessing, annotation, and even though classification requires human efforts. However, afterwards, data piles require being accessible with a standardised API or other channels for better reach to end users.

Role of MindsDB for LLMs: There has been a surge in research focused on the modernization of databases and their integration with machine learning models, including Large Language Models (LLMs), in both academic and developmental fields [6]. One prominent example is the development of MindsDB, which enables the accommodation of data and in-database inferential models in a single platform. In our case, preparing data for LLM training involves several key steps, such as data collection, preprocessing, annotation, classification, and storage (MindsDB). MindsDB can seamlessly integrate incoming Greek data with models that handle preprocessing, annotation, and dialect classification. Moreover, it can facilitate data accessibility through an external API (e.g., GlossAPI), enabling external use of processed data. Considering these functionalities, this study will propose an architectural model designed to meet the requirements of the Greek data pipeline, addressing both input and output interfaces.

This study addresses the creation of a Greek data pile and the associated data management processes aimed at large-scale data collection, preprocessing, annotation, and classification. It also introduces an intelligent, in-database inference tool and presents an architectural model designed to enhance accessibility to the data pile via the GlossAPI, facilitating the seamless addition of new data. We require an intelligent database that can integrate and manage data alongside models for data collection, preprocessing, annotation, and classification in a single location. MindsDB emerges as a top solution to simplify this challenge. It offers multiple interfaces to address the issue, supports a wide variety of input data, and provides in-database inferential capabilities. Additionally, it ensures data accessibility through APIs, enabling an LLM to easily retrieve data for training, fine-tuning, deployment, and version control. Tailored LLMs and their language needs and how language resources developed.

3 research methodology

Figure 1 explains the pipeline developed to prepare the Greek Data for the LLMs by utilizing the in-Database inference technique. It’s a challenging task to collect, clean, and harmonize the data for the LLMs, for a language which has roots in the centuries such as Greek. To make this data pipeline effective for both incoming data and out-going data smooth for the diverse user basis, a methodology

⁴<https://openai.com/index/openai-codex/>

Figure 1: Research methodology for the development of data pipeline and connecting it to in-database inference

Table 1: Data description table being collected for the LLMs

Component	Raw Size	Weight
administration	3.3M	0.000%
ccmatrix	16G	36.99%
elrc_emea	169M	0.39%
elrc_press_releases	1.4M	0.003%
europarl	457M	1.06%
global_voices	28M	0.065%
gnome	385K	0.0009%
nllb	15G	34.69%
paracrawl	4.0G	9.26%
subtitles	6.6G	15.28%
wikimatrix	601M	1.39%
wikipedia	18M	0.041%

has been proposed, is broken down into 4 steps, in this section, each step will be explained in more depth.

3.1 Greek Data Pile Creation

The dataset used in this study was carefully collected from different sources, the quality of the dataset was carefully checked because this data is the basis for the future Greek tailored LLMs development. The description table explaining the corpus collected is given below with the corpus size and weight with respect to whole dataset. This dataset came from diverse sources, that’s why for easy tracking of the resources, we have provided the data resources names as well. After collecting the dataset, it’s mandatory to clean the dataset before feeding it into models or for further processing based on the underlying use cases. We only removed links, or other kinds of noises such as special characters if they are not contributing to the final predictions. The datasets are not comprehensive yet,

but this data collection process is evolving over the time span. It also requires a lot of manual efforts to select the data sources and then check the quality and quantity of data if it qualifies for the LLMs training. For instance, dataset is created from several Greek language collections. This included OPUS collections⁵ as well as other collections originally acquired by GFOSS (including the Greek part of Gutenberg⁶, Greek Legal Code⁷, and Medieval Greek Literature⁸).

There are several challenges with the LLMs data pipeline such as mass data we load, preprocess, and insert data into the database. The full-information regarding the dataset which is being updated quite often is found on GlossAPI project maintained by GFOSS (<https://github.com/eellak/glossAPI/wiki/Guide-to-Datasets>).

⁵<https://opus.nlpl.eu/>

⁶<https://www.gutenberg.org/browse/languages/el>

⁷https://huggingface.co/datasets/greek_legal_code

⁸<http://georgakas.lit.auth.gr/dimodis/>

Table 2: Features extracted from the collected dataset

Types of annotation	Features	Freq	Percentage
Dialect	Classical Greek	19	0.49%
	Modern Dialect (Any)	30	0.78%
	Dialect Free	3796	98.73%
Sociolect	Some Sociolect	103	2.68%
	No sociolect	3743	97.32%
Jargon	Yes	258	6.71%
	No	3588	93.29%
Period	Ancient	3	0.08%
	Demotike	420	10.92%
	Katharevousa	964	25.07%
	Common Modern Greek	2437	63.38%
	Medieval	1	0.03%
	Premedieval	18	0.47%

The collected dataset is not only transferred to better form but also annotation of the collected dataset is performed such as either the dataset instance is dialect (classical Greek, modern dialect, dialect free), sociolect (some sociolect, No sociolect), Jargon (yes, no), and period (ancient, Demotike, Katharevousa, common Greek, medieval, premedieval). These are 13 features associated with each dataset. Table 2 presents roughly 4000 instances of the collected dataset annotated into 13 features by language experts at EELLAK.GR organization and validated by another group. It’s a tremendously tedious task to annotate the datasets manually by keeping nitty gritty of the languages in mind. For instance, the total memory occupied by the collected data in GBs is 42.85 GB. Manually annotating and managing this data is quite a challenging task. The text part of the segments is to be found in official GitHub repo of GlossAPI⁹. The dataset represents about 50% of a corpus with circa 4000 annotated segments, with the following feature distribution as shown in Table 2.

The annotated features come from the composite dataset, described in Unsupervised Dimension Reduction Techniques Outputs.

3.2 Data management

Keeping in view the difficulties while annotating the data into 13 features, there are two kinds of experiments that have been performed using: Unsupervised model and Supervised model. Finally, the developed model (unsupervised and supervised model) is integrated into an intelligent database named MindsDB for efficient in-database inference of incoming new data from sources.

- Unsupervised machine learning: **Composite Dataset** utilized in this experiment can be found on GitHub repository of GlossAPI project¹⁰ Has both the Latent Class predicted class and the coordinates from the Joint Multiple Correspondence Analysis These techniques aim to summarize the labels into a more manageable number of outcome categories, or continuous outcomes. **Discrete** Latent Class Analysis is

a Gaussian Mixture Model, that fits with the Expectation-Maximization Algorithm, and can reveal discrete latent variables in a sample, where the observations are also discrete variables. **Continuous** Correspondence analysis (Joint Multiple Correspondence Analysis) is a geometrical data analysis technique for dimension reduction. Using this technique, we could inspect visual clusters of features, and extract coordinates.

- Supervised deep learning model: The GreekBERT model from HuggingFace¹¹ was finetuned using free-text data to predict the class derived from the Latent Class Analysis. A 3-class solution was determined to be suitable for the 2k dataset¹².
- Integration models and data in MindsDB:

The remaining steps of the proposed methodology diagram are explained in the fourth and fifth sections with all the necessary details from the results achieved from the experiments phase and then challenges faced during the performing these experiments.

4 Results and analysis

4.1 Data annotation and dimension reduction:

Unsupervised Dimension Reduction Techniques Outputs, these coordinates allow projecting the N-feature space onto 2-, 3-, or more dimensional space, and besides visualization, help partition the data according to the resulting visual clusters. Figure 2 shows that the classical Greek dialect from the ancient period (the little cluster in the bottom left) is an outlier to the main body of the observations. Further analysis will possibly reveal more structure in the big cluster in the top right. Language varieties listed from top to bottom in the Figure 2 legend, as used in the dimension reduction, are shown first in Greek and then translated into English as follows: *ἀρχαία* (ancient), *δημοτική* (demotic), *καθαρεύουσα* (Katharevousa, a purist form of Greek that aimed to “cleanse” the language by aligning it with classical Greek),

⁹<https://github.com/eellak/glossAPI/blob/a8a772acb7fcb6c9548f42cdb97479589a65512/data/corpus2k.rda>

¹⁰https://github.com/eellak/glossAPI/blob/a8a772acb7fcb6c9548f42cdb97479589a65512/data/First_dataset/compo_dt.dat

¹¹<https://huggingface.co/nlpaueb/bert-base-greek-uncased-v1>

¹²https://github.com/eellak/glossAPI/tree/a8a772acb7fcb6c9548f42cdb97479589a65512/scripts/models/Greek_BERT_for_regression

Figure 2: Multiple Joint Correspondence Analysis separates a minority of documents from the main corpus and provides coordinates for document features in a n-dimensional space. These are further used for regression or classification inference (e.g., GreekBERT for Regression/Multiple Label Classification, respectively).

ΚοινήΝεοελληνική (KNE)(Common Modern Greek), μεσαιωνική (medieval), and προμεσαιωνική (pre-medieval).

4.2 Greek dialects Data classification

The GreekBERT model from HuggingFace¹³ was finetuned using free-text data to predict the class derived from the Latent Class Analysis. A 3-class solution was determined to be suitable for the 2k dataset. Dataset information for the development of Greek dialects data classification was divided into two sets one set for training with training ratio of 70% and an evaluation set with ratio of 30%. To train the model efficiently and with better accuracy, parameter settings are required, the parameter setting while training the model to classify the Greek dialect classification is shown below:

TrainingArguments(

```
output_dir="./results",
num_train_epochs=10,
per_device_train_batch_size=8, #with 16 also session
was crashing
per_device_eval_batch_size=8,
warmup_steps=500,
weight_decay=0.01,
logging_dir="./logs",
gradient_accumulation_steps=8, # Simulate a larger
batch size
)
```

¹³<https://huggingface.co/nlpaueb/bert-base-greek-uncased-v1>

Figure 3: One running instance of MindsDB in Docker Desktop; red annotations help to understand the environment of MindsDB.

We achieved an evaluation accuracy of 73% after 10 epochs, though this result was likely due to overfitting, as the model struggled to generalize well to new text. Several factors may have contributed to this, including a small number of classes, an unbalanced distribution of features, and latent classes that did not adequately capture the feature space. To address these issues, our team explored two additional methods. The first was BERT for Regression, which aimed to predict the MJCA coordinates from free text but failed to converge to a solution. The second was GreekLegalRoberta for Sequence Classification, which focuses on ruling out Ancient Greek as a preliminary step¹⁴. We chose this model because its tokenizer performs better with Greek-language corpora. This latter approach essentially treats the ancient dialect as spam, flagging it for exclusion during LLM training. Our work on this is still in progress, and we will report further findings in a forthcoming paper currently under preparation.

Time and space constraints: Training and fine-tuning require sufficient RAM to load the model (e.g., Meltemi Mini version requires almost 15+ GB of RAM to load the model for simple testing - we tried this experiment for the exploration purposes). More than that, to run an instance of MindsDB, you also need a large chunk of memory. The training of the BERTGreek was significantly longer; it took almost 5 hours for just a small number of observations. So, it's much more optimal to say that it's difficult to load, fine-tune and deploy the LLMs with fewer resources. Mostly, to fine-tune or deploy an LLM, the GPUs are pre-requisitioned.

4.3 Integrating models and data into MindsDB

An intelligent database named MindsDB, which provides not only storage for data but also in-database inference engines—OpenAI and custom models integration, such as “Bring Your Own Model (BYOM)” in the MindsDB environment. MindsDB capabilities were accessed by installing and testing it at GFOSS premises in the production environment using Docker. MindsDB creates engines when integrating a model into its environment, and from these engines, it develops respective models. These models can be utilized for a range of tasks, such as automated fine-tuning, AI agents, AI-powered data retrieval, data enrichment, predictive analytics, in-database machine learning, and AI workflow automation.

The overall aim is to bring the Greek data within the MindsDB environment and automate the data steps (cleaning, annotation, and classification) using the existing AI models or LLMs. The in-database inference models are appealing because of their potential in enhancing FAIR data provision capabilities alongside integration with LLMs. A simple snapshot of the mindsdb working with stored data and AI models is shown in Figure 3, where we selected already the available models in the MindsDB AI engines space and then selecting the data from the existing data source and the output of the model is shown below, which can further be stored along with the data itself.

¹⁴https://huggingface.co/datasets/glossAPI/95k_deigma_ellinikis; https://github.com/eellak/glossAPI/tree/7b423d8dd458fb67c87c63ba0f73a405ebcd5d65/Greek_variety_classification

Figure 4: An Architecture for the development of Greek Data Pile and provision to the external users (data, LLMs, and applications) (Source: author)

5 Architecture for the creation of Greek pile for LLMs

Based on the research objectives, two distinct requirements emerge for the Greek data pile: first, the need for extensive data collection and storage, and second, the necessity for intelligent models to preprocess, annotate, and classify various Greek dialects. In addition to these needs, there is also a requirement to accommodate incoming data and facilitate its delivery to different applications and LLMs through the development of GlossAPI. These requirements have been incorporated in the proposed architectural model as shown in Figure 4. This model is undergoing a thorough check of effectiveness and integration capabilities with diverse data sources and intelligent models. A data pipeline developed by adopting this architectural model significantly enhances the Greek data pile’s accessibility not for LLMs only but beyond.

There are three main layers in the architectural model as explained below:

- **MindsDB:** Supports the storage of Greek Data pile along with intelligent models (supervised, unsupervised, LLMs, etc.).
- **GlossAPI:** Make a bridge connection through API interfaces to access the Greek data pile.
- **Integration Layer:** This layer makes the integration of the GlossAPI connection with the other data sources, applications, and even other LLMs to explore and utilise the Greek Data pile.

6 discussion

This study delves into the creation of Greek data piles, which are specifically necessary for the training of LLMs. Additionally, it is a component of the ongoing GlossAPI project, which is led by "The

Open Technologies Alliance (GFOSS)." This project is not a solitary task; it encompasses much more, as this study has demonstrated. The project involved creating a Greek data pile, a highly challenging task. Creating not only a quantity-focused data pile, but also unbiased and error-free Greek data is of utmost importance. The team at GFOSS is diligently working to collect this data in an efficient manner, but they are dedicating a significant amount of time to prepare and pipeline it for external use, particularly for the creation of Greek open source LLMs, which are the ultimate output of the GlossAPI project. Through this study, we have seen that several tasks, such as data preprocessing, data annotation, classification, and even the storage of the data pile, can be automated by using the intelligent database, which can perform actions on the incoming data as specified in the data pipeline.

We have proposed and developed a small case study using an intelligent database called MindsDB, which can accommodate all these functionalities (preprocessing, annotation, classification, and storage) and the Greek data pile at the same time. Figure 4 displays the entire conceptual model of this proposed work, providing a detailed explanation of each module. However, a fully-fledged implementation of this architectural model is required in the near future. If this pipeline succeeds, it will replace a significant amount of manual work for creating data piles with automated and in-database operations. This study has both theoretical and professional implications. This study has theoretical implications by providing an architecture to develop Greek data pile which can further be utilised for the development of LLMs and also can make the clean and structured Greek data available for other tasks. Practically speaking, it can assist in transforming Greek data into a format suitable for LLM training and other applications. In addition, this pipeline can also be integrated with other applications and data

itself. It will also resolve the complexity of the data preparation tasks practically; for instance, it has well-defined steps, and each team can work on specific tasks to accomplish the Greek data pile and serving the data pile for the development of open-source LLMs. The GlossAPI architecture enhances the flexibility of the Greek data pile by enabling the efficient selection of optimal training examples for Large Language Models (LLMs) in common Modern Greek, free from dialect, sociolect, and jargon influences. It later supports the addition of balanced samples to the training set, allowing the model to achieve stylistic variation and flexibility while preserving the core linguistic standards. For this reason, implementation of intermediate modular architecture proposed in Figure 4, that will assist in selecting the training and validation dataset from a database that contains a broad range of examples found in the wild, including unsuitable varieties of Greek.

7 Conclusion and future work

This study sets the groundwork for the creation of a Greek data pile to serve the needs for open-source Greek LLM training. We set three objectives to fulfill in this research: RO1 is to create the Greek data pile; RO2 is data management through preprocessing, annotation, classification, and storage; and RO3 is architectural model development to automate the RO1 and RO2 by bringing the intelligent databases into action. This study explained the steps being performed to create the Greek data pile, which is evolving quickly over time. The selection of data sources, collecting and fetching the Greek data and storage into a structured and well-documented format to keep track of the datasets as well. Several steps in the current scenario while creation of the Greek data pile is done manually, which are time- and resource-consuming. Keeping in mind that time consumption and resource exhaustion, this study proposed and developed an architecture that can serve the needs for the Greek data pile creation as well as the data usage by the external use. In this regard, we have developed small models for the data annotation and classification of Greek dialects as shown in Table 2. The annotation and classification tasks are hectic some when incoming data is massive, so model integration within databases can help to clean and moderate the Greek data pile creation. We have shown the working functionality of MindsDB as well as how it works with the data stored within it. And how it can be scalable for future tasks.

As stated, before in this study, this project is gigantic and requires a lot of effort both in terms of time and resources; the architectural model requires to be fully functional and tested with real-time operations is the future work of this study. Also, the models explored until now are related to annotation, dimensionality reduction, and classification; these models require to be improved and integrated with the architectural model. Finally, using the Greek data pile, an open source LLM is the ultimate goal of the GlossAPI project, which will come in the future.

One other possible future direction is to include open data portals and their interoperability as a data source for the data pile in general to develop data products swiftly. This connection comes from the usage of MindsDB as a data warehousing software that can accommodate open data and different intelligent models, including LLMs. As a data warehouse, it can provide an endpoint for open data

portals, and with the right metadata ontology, its AI integrations can help promote the understanding of open-linked data. I mean, it can help generalize metadata descriptions to databases with the AI integration.

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